

Research Article

Influence of 10.7 cm Solar Radio Flux on Some Light Trapped Insect Species from Australia, Europe and North America

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Abstract

The present study deals with the connection of 10.7 cm solar radio flux and light-trap catches of insect species from three continents: Australia, Europe and North America.

For each moth (Lepidoptera) and caddisfly (Trichoptera) species, a relationship was found between the 10.7 cm solar radio flux and the number of insects captured. However, the relationships were not identical.

Keywords: 10.7 cm solar radio flux, light-trap, moths, caddisfly

Introduction

The activity of the Sun is the common name for a group of local disturbances of the Sun's radiation. Electromagnetic and corpuscular radiation from the Sun changes the geophysical parameters on Earth. These can be followed by changes in the biosphere's phenomena. The solar activity contains all the information about the Sun's surface detected by using several methods.

Among them, the most important is the appearance of sunspots, which has been continuously observed since the 18th century. They peak approximately every 11.2 years.

The generally accepted index-number of sunspots is the Wolf-type relative number (RW).

[1], introduced the concept of Q-index ($Q = i \times t$), to quantify the daily flare activity through the 24 hours of the day. In this relation, "i" represents the intensity scale of importance and "t" the duration (in minutes) of the flare. Some researchers of flare activity using Kleczek's method are [2-4]. The Hungarian researcher, [5] also calculated and published the "Flare Activity Numbers" based on similar theoretical principles as the Q-index for the period of 1957-1961.

The effect of solar activity on insects has also been studied by several researchers [6-8]. However, these studies focused primarily on insect gradations. Apart from our own work, we cannot refer to studies that investigate the effectiveness of insect trapping in the context of solar activity. In recent years, we have examined the light trapping of insects in relation to all solar activity index numbers. We found that sunspot numbers affect the light trapping of many moth (Microlepidoptera) species [9]. It was also found

that the flight activity to light traps by the Micro- and Macrolepidoptera species is affected by Flare Activity Numbers [10]. The Q-index numbers also affect the light trapping of many insect species [11-13].

In the present study, we examined the numbers of some moth and a caddisfly species from Australia, Europe and North America, caught by light-traps in context of a previously unused Sun index, the 10.7 cm solar radio flux.

Material

The solar radio flux at 10.7 cm (2800 MHz) is an excellent indicator of solar activity. The F10.7 correlates well with the sunspot number as well as a number of ultraviolet (UV) and visible solar irradiance records. The F10.7 has been measured consistently in Canada since 1947, first at Ottawa, Ontario and then at the Penticton Radio Observatory in British Columbia, Canada. Unlike many solar indices, the F10.7 radio flux can easily be measured reliably on a day-to-day basis from the Earth's surface, in all types of weather.

The data we use was published by British Geological Survey (http://www.geomag.bgs.ac.uk/data_service/space_weather/solar.html)

Lionel Hill collected insects by the Rothamsted type light-trap in Australia (Tasmania, Stony Rise) between 1992 and 2018.

In Hungary (Central Europe) a standardised network of agricultural and forestry light-traps operated from 1958 until the present.

In two states of the USA (Nebraska and North Carolina) for many years, moth (Lepidoptera), beetle (Coleoptera) and bug (Heteroptera) species have been light trapped in several places.

In Hungary many caddisflies (Trichoptera) were collected for many years by Ottó Kiss.

Several aspects were considered in the selection of the insect species to be included in the study. The moth species were selected from light-trap collection data from three continents. We included a species (*Ostrinia nubilalis* Hbn.) that is native to both Europe and North America. An important consideration in selecting moth species was to have pests that could be collected en masse.

We selected species from each of the three continents that have taxonomic affinities (Noctuidae, Heliiothinae). This allowed us to study whether their responses to this environmental impact differed.

We also observed that the selected species should represent as many taxa as possible and include migratory species (*Plutella xylostella* L., *Helicoverpa punctigera* Wallengren, *Persectania ewingii* Westwood).

The number of caught individuals and their catch data are shown in Table 1 for the selected species.

Table 1: Catching data of examined moth (Lepidoptera) and caddisfly (Trichoptera) species

Species	Number of	
	Specimens	Data
Australia (Tasmania, Stony Rise)		
Plutellidae		
Diamond-back Moth (<i>Plutella xylostella</i> Linnaeus, 1758)	15,909	1,095
Crambidae, Pyraustinae		
Tree Lucerne Moth (<i>Uresiphita ornithopteralis</i> Guenée, 1854)	2,778	1,289
Noctuidae, Heliiothinae		
Australian Native Budworm (<i>Helicoverpa punctigera</i> Wallengren, 1860)	3,823	2,035
Noctuidae, Hadeninae		
Southern Armyworm (<i>Persectania ewingii</i> Westwood, 1839)	7,433	1,809
Europe (Hungary)		
Trichoptera, Hydropsychidae		
Hydropsyche instabilis Curtis, 1834	29,405	507
Lepidoptera: Crambidae, Pyraustinae		
European Corn-borer (<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> Hübner, 1790)	309,873	72,187
Microlepidoptera spec. indet.	590,159	21,761
Noctuidae, Heliiothinae		
Scarce Bordered Straw (<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> Hübner, 1808)	25,531	6,754
North America (USA: Nebraska and North Carolina)		
Lepidoptera: Crambidae, Pyraustinae		
European Corn-borer (<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> Hübner, 1790)	81,501	3,768
Erebidae, Erebininae		
Forage Looper (<i>Caenurgia erechtea</i> Cramer, 1780)	14,310	1,1243
Noctuidae, Heliiothinae		

Corn Earworm (<i>Heliothis zea</i> Boddie, 1850)	75,630	2,205
Noctuidae, Noctuinae		
Western Bean Cutworm (<i>Striacosta albicosta</i> Smith, 1888)	61,851	955

Methods

Basic data were the number of individuals and species caught in one night. In order to compare the differing sampling data, relative values were calculated from the number of individuals separately for each species for each sampling night per year. The relative catch value (RC) was defined as the quotient of the number of specimens caught during a sampling time unit (1 night) per the average nightly catch of individuals and species within the relevant sampling period. For example, when the actual nightly catch was equal to the average nightly catch in the relevant summer, the RC was 1 [14].

Separately, all catch data by species were considered as a single sample and thus relative catch values were calculated.

This solution also made it possible to determine the effectiveness of trapping from the relative catch values of each year and to compare the effectiveness of the years.

We made divisions using Sturges' method [15]. Finally, we averaged within groups the 10.7 cm solar radio flux and relative catch data pairs.

Results and Discussion

Our results can be seen in Figures 1-12.

Figure 1 Light-trap catch of Diamond-back Moth (*Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus, 1758) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Figure 2 Light-trap catch of Tree Lucerne Moth (*Uresiphita ornithopteralis* Guenée, 1854) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Figure 3 Light-trap catch of Australian Native Budworm (*Helicoverpa punctigera* Wallegren, 1860) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Figure 7 Light-trap catch of *Microlepidoptera* spec. indet. in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Figure 4 Light-trap catch of Southern Armyworm (*Persectaria ewingii* Westwood, 1839) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Figure 8 Light-trap catch of Scarce Bordered Straw (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hübner, 1808) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Figure 5 Light-trap catch of *Hydropsyche instabilis* Curtis, 1834 in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Figure 9 Light-trap catch of European Corn-borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis* Hübner, 1796) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux (Nebraska and North Carolina)

Figure 6 Light-trap catch of European Corn-borer (*Ostrinia nubilalis* Hübner) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux (Hungary)

Figure 10 Light-trap catch of Forage Looper (*Caenurgia erechtea* Cramer, 1780) in connection with the 10.7 cm solar radio flux

Our investigations prove that the catching results of species are extremely different. There are also similar forms, but this is not always related to taxonomic affinity. It is true that the catch of two American noctuid moth (*Heliothis zea* Boddie and *Striacosta albicosta* Smith) initially rises in parallel with the increasing values of the solar radio flux and then decreases sharply. However, *Plutella xylostella* L., which is light trapped in Australia, behaves in the same way. This result is not easy to explain.

The results of the *Ostrinia nubilalis* Hbn. and *Heliothis armigera* Hbn., which are light-trapped in Hungary, are very similar to this form. For these species, the reduction in catch is not so drastic. Catches of two moths and one caddisfly species collected in Hungary, as well as one moth collected in Australia, are high only when solar activity is weak and then low. Only one moth species (*Uresiphita ornithopteralis* Guenée) trapped in Australia, can be caught in relatively high numbers when solar activity is high. The catch of *Heliothis zea* Boddie shows two catch peaks. We explain these very different results based on our previous hypothesis.

According to our hypothesis, the explanation of our results can be the following:

The low relative catch values always refer to weather situations in which the flight activity of insects diminishes. However, high values are not so clear to interpret. Major environmental changes bring about physiological transformation in the insect organism. The imago is short-lived, therefore unfavorable weather endangers the survival of not just the individual, but the species as a whole. In our hypothesis, the individual may adopt two kinds of strategies to evade the impacts hindering the normal functioning of its life phenomena. It may either display more liveliness, by increasing the intensity of its flight, copulation and egg-laying activity or take refuge

in passivity from weather an unfavorable situation. And so, by the present state of our knowledge we might say that favorable and unfavorable weather situations might equally be accompanied by a high catch [14]. This behavior may be true for all the examined species particularly ones with two catching peaks [16, 17].

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